

Sustainable improvement of INTERprofessional care for better resident outcomes: SCALing up an Evidence-based care model for nursing homes (INTERSCALE). A protocol for a scoping literature review

This protocol followed the Unified Management, Assessment and Review of Information (SUMARI) guidelines and template from the Joanna Briggs Institute.

Vanessa Litschgi¹, Franziska Zúñiga¹, Thekla Brunkert^{1,2}, Sabina De Geest^{1,3}, Michael Simon¹, Sandra Staudacher^{1,4}, Reto W. Kressig^{2,5}, Nathalie I.H. Wellens⁶, Christine Serdaly⁷, Jana Bartakova^{1,8}, Raphaëlle Ashley Guerbaai¹

¹Institute of Nursing Science, University of Basel, Switzerland

²University Department of Geriatric Medicine FELIX PLATTER, Basel, Switzerland

³Public Health and Primary Care, Academic Centre for Nursing and Midwifery, KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium

⁴Department of Health Services Research, Care and Public Health Research Institute, Maastricht University, Maastricht, The Netherlands

⁵Faculty of Medicine, University of Basel, Basel, Switzerland.

⁶La Source School of Nursing, HES-SO University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Western Switzerland, Lausanne, Switzerland

⁷Serdaly&Ankers snc, Conches, Switzerland

⁸Institute of Biophysics and Informatics, 1st Faculty of Medicine, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic

Abstract

Objective: The goal of this scoping review is to identify and describe implementation strategies used to support the implementation of complex interventions in nursing homes (NHs) aiming at reducing unplanned transfers.

Introduction: Unplanned transfers are burdensome for NH residents and can lead to adverse outcomes. In the last decade, an increasing number of programs have addressed this issue and complex interventions have been developed, such as nurse-led care models, to reduce unplanned transfers. The preparation to scale-up complex interventions requires detailed knowledge about which implementation strategies might best support their implementation.

Methods: The Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) methodology for scoping reviews will be followed. Three themes: “Nursing homes”, “Unplanned Hospitalizations/transfers” and “Implementation science/implementation strategies” will guide the search strategy development for this scoping review. Sources include electronic databases (Cochrane, Medline, CINAHL, PsychINFO, Scopus) and grey literature. It will take place between April and November 2022. Studies will be included if they describe implementation strategies used to implement (complex) interventions targeting the reduction of unplanned hospital transfers from NHs. The full texts will be assessed by two or more independent reviewers. Data extraction for the included studies will follow the JBI data extraction instrument.

Ethics and dissemination: This scoping review does not require ethics approval because it collects data from publicly available literature. Findings will offer insights to inform discussions with NH stakeholders and will be disseminated through conference presentations and an open-access publication in a peer-reviewed journal.

Introduction

Implementation Science is defined as the study of methods to support the systematic uptake of evidence-based interventions into policy and practice [1]. Implementation Science seeks to close the gap between what we *know* and what we *do* (often referred to as “the know-do gap”) by identifying and addressing the barriers that slow or halt the uptake of proven health interventions and evidence-based practices [1]. This enables a better understanding of why the intervention succeeded or, on the contrary, (partially) failed. Methodological elements include a theory-driven contextual analysis and the use of implementation strategies. The former drives the development of contextually tailored interventions and implementation strategies, while the latter is key for the adoption, implementation, sustainment, and scale-up of a program [2, 3].

A case-in-point are nurse-led care models that effectively reduce unplanned transfers to hospitals from NHs. Indeed, transfers from NHs are burdensome, associated with adverse outcomes for residents such as falls, delirium, or nosocomial infections; and are costly for the health system [4, 5]. A number of nurse-led care models have been developed and proved effective in reducing unplanned hospital transfers and improved the quality of care in NHs [4, 6–11]. One of these models was INTERCARE, which was developed and tested in Switzerland to reduce unplanned transfers from NHs [12–14]. The Improving INTERprofessionalCARE for better resident outcomes (INTERCARE), is a complex intervention that supports the working with registered nurses in expanded roles and includes six key components 1) interprofessional collaboration, 2) INTERCARE nurse 3) comprehensive geriatric assessment, 4) evidence-based tools [15] 5) advance care planning (ACP), and 6) data-driven quality improvement. INTERCARE showed effectiveness in reducing unplanned transfers in the eleven participating NHs [12], confirming results of similar models in the US (e.g., MOQI). INTERCARE showed high sustainability among the participating NHs and given its clinical effectiveness, has the potential for scale-up in Switzerland [12].

The set of implementation strategies – developed based on scientific evidence and a thorough contextual analysis [16] – were deemed important and necessary by the NHs to successfully reduce unplanned transfers [12], maintain a high degree of fidelity to most of the core elements of INTERCARE (e.g., Interprofessional collaboration [17]), and sustain the model after the end of the study period. These strategies included, e.g., a tailored curriculum to train INTERCARE nurses, leadership support meetings and provision of material [18]. Common implementation strategies reported in studies which aim to reduce unplanned transfers include strategies that support multidisciplinary teams [20], teaching and coaching for nurses working in extended roles [20] or onsite champions [10]. In order for nurse-led care models like INTERCARE and

other programs addressing unplanned transfers to be scaled up to a larger group of NHs, whilst maintaining effectiveness, fitting implementation strategies need to be selected that can be broadly applied [19].

Research gap

Intervention scale-up can fail due to the lack of evidence on the best strategies for implementing an evidence-based intervention, and to tackle the complexity of multi-component interventions which require tailoring and continual adaptations to individual or organizational needs and target multiple levels [21, 22]. This underpins the need to better understand which implementation strategies were effectively used in different programs to reduce unplanned transfers [23]. A scoping review was chosen as it will enable an overview of the scope of available literature pertaining to the usage of implementations strategies in NHs concerning this issue. Based on our preliminary searches, we expect a broad range of programs that aim to reduce unplanned transfers with different core elements and implementation strategies, which will not allow us to do a meta-analysis concerning the effectiveness of the latter.

Review question

Aims

The aim of this scoping review is to provide a comprehensive synthesis of the evidence concerning implementation strategies that support the implementation of complex interventions to reduce unplanned transfers from NHs. The review is guided by the following research questions:

- 1) Which implementation strategies are used in complex interventions to reduce unplanned transfers from nursing homes?
- 2) What is the impact of these implementation strategies on the implementation of the complex interventions (including implementation outcomes such as fidelity, feasibility, acceptability, etc.)?
- 3) What are the costs of individual implementation strategies and the cost-effectiveness of these?

Keywords

Complex interventions; implementation strategies; nursing homes; unplanned transfers

Eligibility criteria

Inclusion criteria

Original studies or reviews will be included if they describe implementation strategies used to implement interventions targeting the reduction of unplanned hospital transfers from NHs (Table 1). Unplanned transfers refer to all transfers from the nursing home to an acute care setting for an unplanned reason (i.e., after a fall) resulting in either an emergency department visit only or a hospitalization. A nursing home refers to an institution providing residential accommodation with 24h-healthcare for older adults. Implementation strategies, are defined as methods or techniques described used to enhance the adoption, implementation, and sustainability of an intervention in a given setting [23]. General and detailed information concerning methodology, aims, outcomes and results will form part of the documentation, including a structured description of the implementation strategies applied and of barriers and facilitators addressed with the use of implementation strategies.

Exclusion criteria

Studies that do not report implementation strategies, the implementation of an intervention, measure unplanned or avoidable hospital transfers or that do take place in other settings than NHs will be excluded.

Table 1: Exclusion and inclusion criteria based on the PICO Framework [24]

PICO Element	Inclusion/exclusion criteria
Population/ participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nursing homes / NH residents with any condition (e.g., dementia, frailty) <i>Excluded: Hospices, residential homes, assisted living, transitional care settings, geriatric hospitals</i>
Interventions/ Exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation strategies addressing complex interventions aiming at reducing unplanned transfers from NHs. Implementation strategies can be at the macro (e.g., financial model for nurse experts/ care model, regulation of hospitalisations), meso (e.g., preparatory coaching to help NHs to introduce a complex intervention), or micro level (e.g., teaching individual geriatric nurse experts to reflect on causal factors for hospitalisations) <i>Excluded: studies examining interventions to reduce unplanned ED admissions / hospitalizations that do not describe the implementation strategies used</i>
Comparators/ controls	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Usual care or none
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unplanned ED admissions/ hospitalizations as primary or secondary outcome <i>Excluded: Studies that did not report or evaluate unplanned or avoidable transfers</i>

Study designs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Randomized controlled trials (RCTs); non-RCTs; quasi-experimental study designs (e.g., controlled before-after studies); comparative cohort studies; mixed-method studies • Protocols of studies with any of the above-mentioned designs • <i>Excluded: Cross-sectional, case-control, case reports</i>
----------------------	---

Methods

The proposed scoping review will be conducted in accordance with the Joanna Briggs Institute methodology for scoping reviews [25].

Search strategy

The search strategy will consist of terms (MeSH and free text) covering three themes: “Nursing homes”, “Unplanned Hospitalizations/transfers” and “Implementation science and implementation strategies/interventions” (see Appendix 1). Sources include electronic databases (Cochrane, Medline via Pubmed, CINAHL via EBSCOhost, PsychINFO via OVID, Scopus). The reference lists of all selected literature will be hand searched for additional literature. Further, any additional grey literature will be searched through Google. No filters will be applied. Studies published in English, French, German, Italian, Czech or Spanish will be included as these languages are covered by the members of the INTERSCALE research group. Studies published from inception until the database search will be included.

The literature review search began in April 2022 with unsystematic online research in PubMed, PubReMiner, and Google scholar to find important key terms and synonyms, which was supported by brainstorming in the research group to add more relevant key terms. Subsequently, we combine the set of terms with “OR” to build the concept sets by each group member and then discuss the results in the research group. The final search string will be developed by combining the concept sets with “AND.” An auto alert for each database will be set with the following search strings until End of November 2022.

The initial database to search will be PubMed, the search string will subsequently be translated for the other databases. Once all search strings are developed, they will be re-run concurrently on the same day with these final results being further processed after removal of duplicates.

The review will occur between April and October 2022. The protocol will be published on the web-platform Zenodo [26]. Prior to starting this protocol, a preliminary search was performed in Pubmed to identify whether a similar review had been conducted. Additionally, the authors checked the PROSPERO register, the Johanna-Briggs-Institute (JBI) register for systematic

reviews, the Open Science Foundation registry and Zenodo and no similar protocol has been registered.

Evidence selection

Following the search, all identified citations will be collated and uploaded into the Rayyan tool [27] to organize and manage the collaborative literature review, and duplicates removed. Following a pilot test, titles and abstracts will then be screened by two or more independent reviewers for assessment against the inclusion criteria for the review. Potentially relevant sources will be retrieved in full. The full text of selected citations will be assessed in detail against the inclusion criteria by two or more independent reviewers. Reasons for exclusion of sources of evidence at full text that do not meet the inclusion criteria will be recorded and reported in the scoping review. Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers at each stage of the selection process will be resolved through discussion, or with an additional reviewer/s. The results of the search and the study inclusion process will be reported in full in the final scoping review and presented in a Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses extension for scoping review (PRISMA-ScR) flow diagram [28].

Data extraction

Data extraction for the included studies will follow the JBI data extraction instrument [25] and entered in an electronic spreadsheet. The following information will be added: outcomes measured and implementation strategies supporting the implementation. The implementation strategies will be differentiated according to whether resources needed to support the implementation strategies were external to the nursing home (e.g., study nurse, external coach), internal (e.g., trained colleague) or a mix of both. The implementation strategies will be defined and operationalized according to Proctor et al.'s framework [29] and the Expert Recommendations for Implementing Change (ERIC) taxonomy will be used for a mapping of the implementation strategies. Data extraction will be performed by a primary reviewer and checked by a secondary reviewer. Disagreement will be resolved during a discussion with a third reviewer. We will not enquire about any non-reported results from the study authors.

Data Analysis and Presentation

A PRISMA flow chart will be used to summarize the data collection process and justify the number of included and excluded studies from this review. From the included literature we would like to create an overview of the implementation strategies used. A narrative synthesis will give an overall assessment of the implementation strategies used to support the implementation of interventions; and of the evidence for the effectiveness of described implementation strategies.

Funding

INTERSCALE is funded by the Swiss Nursing Science Foundation.

Conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest for this proposed scoping review.

Dissemination

This literature review will be submitted to a scientific journal once completed.

References

- [1] University of Washington. What is Implementation Science?: An Introduction to the Science; 2022 [cited 2022 July 5] Available from: URL: <https://impsciuw.org/implementation-science/learn/implementation-science-overview/>.
- [2] Rabin BA, Brownson RC, Haire-Joshu D, Kreuter MW, Weaver NL. A glossary for dissemination and implementation research in health. *J Public Health Manag Pract* 2008; 14(2): 117–23 [<https://doi.org/10.1097/01.PHH.0000311888.06252.bb>][PMID: 18287916]
- [3] Wolfenden L, Foy R, Pesseau J, Grimshaw JM, Ivers NM, Powell BJ, Taljaard M, Wiggers J, Sutherland R, Nathan N, Williams CM, Kingsland M, Milat A, Hodder RK, Yoong S. Designing and undertaking randomised implementation trials: guide for researchers. *BMJ* 2021; 372: m3721 [<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m3721>][PMID: 33461967]
- [4] Dwyer T, Craswell A, Rossi D, Holzberger D. Evaluation of an aged care nurse practitioner service: quality of care within a residential aged care facility hospital avoidance service. *BMC Health Services Research* 2017; 17(1): 33 [<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-017-1977-x>][PMID: 28086869]
- [5] Muench U, Simon M, Guerbaai RA, Carlo de P, Zeller A, Kressig RW, Zúñiga F. Preventable hospitalizations from ambulatory care sensitive conditions in nursing homes: evidence from Switzerland. *Int J Public Health* 2019; 64(9): 1273–81 [<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00038-019-01294-1>][PMID: 31482196]
- [6] Giebel C, Harvey D, Akpan A, Chamberlain P. Reducing hospital admissions in older care home residents: a 4-year evaluation of the care home innovation Programme (CHIP). *BMC Health Services Research* 2020; 20(1): 94 [<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-020-4945-9>][PMID: 32028940]
- [7] Kane RL, Flood S, Bershadsky B, Keckhafer G. Effect of an innovative medicare managed care program on the quality of care for nursing home residents. *Gerontologist* 2004; 44(1): 95–103 [<https://doi.org/10.1093/geront/44.1.95>][PMID: 14978325]
- [8] Kim H, Jung YI, Kim G-S, Choi H, Park YH. Effectiveness of a Technology-Enhanced Integrated Care Model for Frail Older People: A Stepped-Wedge Cluster Randomized Trial in Nursing Homes. *Gerontologist* 2021; 61(3): 460–9 [<https://doi.org/10.1093/geront/gnaa090>][PMID: 32668005]
- [9] Lacny S, Zarrabi M, Martin-Misener R, Faith D, Sketris I, Murphy A, DiCenso A, Marshall D. Cost-effectiveness of a nurse practitioner-family physician model of care in a nursing home: controlled before and after study. *J Adv Nurs* 2016; 72(9): 2138–52 [<https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.12989>][PMID: 27119440]
- [10] Rantz MJ, Popejoy L, Vogelsmeier A, Galambos C, Alexander G, Flesner M, Crecelius C, Ge B, Petroski G. Successfully Reducing Hospitalizations of Nursing Home Residents: Results of the Missouri Quality Initiative. *J Am Med Dir Assoc* 2017; 18(11): 960–6 [<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jamda.2017.05.027>][PMID: 28757334]
- [11] Arendts G, Etherton-Beer C, Howard K, Lewin G, Sim M, Pickstock S, Fitzhardinge S, O'Brien K, Tassell S, Deans P, Blackwell, S. Nurse led care coordination: trial protocol and development of a best practice resource guide for a cluster controlled clinical trial in Australian aged care facilities. *Arch Gerontol Geriatr* 2014; 58(1): 15–9 [<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.archger.2013.07.004>][PMID: 23972906]
- [12] Zúñiga F, Guerbaai RA, De Geest S, Popejoy L, Bartakova J, Denhaerynck K, Trutschel D, Basinska K, Nicca D, Kressig RW, Zeller A, Wellens NIH, De Pietro C, Desmedt M, Serdaly C, Simon, M. Positive effect of the INTERCARE nurse-led model on reducing nursing home transfers: A

- nonrandomized stepped-wedge design. *J Am Geriatr Soc* 2022; 70(5): 1546–57
[<https://doi.org/10.1111/jgs.17677>][PMID: 35122238]
- [13] Basinska K, Wellens NIH, Simon M, Zeller A, Kressig RW, Zúñiga F. Registered nurses in expanded roles improve care in nursing homes: Swiss perspective based on the modified Delphi method. *J Adv Nurs* 2021; 77(2): 742–54
[<https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.14644>][PMID: 33222269]
- [14] Zúñiga F, De Geest S, Guerbaai RA, Basinska K, Nicca D, Kressig RW, Zeller A, Wellens NIH, De Pietro C, Vlaeyen E, Desmedt M, Serdaly C, Simon M. Strengthening Geriatric Expertise in Swiss Nursing Homes: INTERCARE Implementation Study Protocol. *J Am Geriatr Soc* 2019; 67(10): 2145–50
[<https://doi.org/10.1111/jgs.16074>][PMID: 31317544]
- [15] Ouslander JG, Bonner A, Herndon L, Shutes J. The Interventions to Reduce Acute Care Transfers (INTERACT) quality improvement program: an overview for medical directors and primary care clinicians in long term care. *J Am Med Dir Assoc* 2014; 15(3): 162–70
[<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jamda.2013.12.005>][PMID: 24513226]
- [16] Basinska K, Guerbaai RA, Simon M, De Geest S, Wellens NIH, Serdaly C, De Pietro C, Desmedt M, Kressig RW, Nicca D, Zeller A, Vaes A, Zúñiga F. A nurse-led care model to strengthen geriatric expertise in nursing homes: The development and content of the INTERCARE model. Basel: Medical Faculty, Institute of Nursing Science, University of Basel; 2021.
- [17] Guerbaai RA., DeGeest S, M. Simon., Wellens NIH, Denhaerynck K, Zúñiga. F. Implementation fidelity to a complex intervention reducing unplanned hospitalisations: A mixed-methods study of the INTERCARE nurse-led care model.: In preparation. 2022.; 2022.
- [18] Rolland Y, Tavassoli N, De Souto Barreto P, Perrin A, Laffon de Mazières C, Rapp T, Hermabessière S, Tournay E, Vellas B, Andrieu S. Systematic Dementia Screening by Multidisciplinary Team Meetings in Nursing Homes for Reducing Emergency Department Transfers: The IDEM Cluster Randomized Clinical Trial. *JAMA Netw Open* 2020; 3(2): e200049
[<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.0049>][PMID: 32101308]
- [19] WHO Regional Office for Europe. Scaling up projects and initiatives for better health: from concepts to practice; 2016.
- [20] Hickman SE, Unroe KT, Ersek M, Stump TE, Tu W, Ott M, Sachs GA. Systematic Advance Care Planning and Potentially Avoidable Hospitalizations of Nursing Facility Residents. *J Am Geriatr Soc* 2019; 67(8): 1649–55 [<https://doi.org/10.1111/jgs.15927>][PMID: 31012971]
- [21] Chambers DA, Glasgow RE, Stange KC. The dynamic sustainability framework: addressing the paradox of sustainment amid ongoing change; 2013.
- [22] Craig P, Dieppe P, Macintyre S, Michie S, Nazareth I, Petticrew M. Developing and evaluating complex interventions: the new Medical Research Council guidance. *BMJ* 2008; 337: a1655
[<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.a1655>][PMID: 18824488]
- [23] Curran GM, Bauer M, Mittman B, Pyne JM, Stetler C. Effectiveness-implementation hybrid designs: combining elements of clinical effectiveness and implementation research to enhance public health impact. *Med Care* 2012; 50(3): 217–26
[<https://doi.org/10.1097/MLR.0b013e3182408812>][PMID: 22310560]
- [24] Miller SA, Forrest JL. Enhancing your practice through evidence-based decision making: PICO, learning how to ask good questions. *Journal of Evidence Based Dental Practice* 2001; 1(2): 136–41 [[https://doi.org/10.1016/S1532-3382\(01\)70024-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1532-3382(01)70024-3)]
- [25] Aromataris E, Munn Z. *JBIM Manual for Evidence Synthesis*. JBI 2020.
- [26] European Organization for Nuclear Research, OpenAIRE. Zenodo. CERN; 2013.

- [27] Ouzzani M, Hammady H, Fedorowicz Z, Elmagarmid A. Rayyan-a web and mobile app for systematic reviews. *Syst Rev* 2016; 5(1): 210
[<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-016-0384-4>][PMID: 27919275]
- [28] Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, O'Brien KK, Colquhoun H, Levac D, Moher D, Peters MDJ, Horsley T, Weeks L, Hempel S, Akl, EA, Chang C, McGowan J, Stewart L, Hartling L, Aldcroft A, Wilson MG, Garritty C, Lewin S, Godfrey CM, Macdonald MT, Langlois EV, Soares-Weiser K, Moriarty J, Clifford T, Tunçalp Ö, Straus SE. PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and Explanation. *Ann Intern Med* 2018; 169(7): 467–73
[<https://doi.org/10.7326/M18-0850>][PMID: 30178033]
- [29] Proctor EK, Powell BJ, McMillen JC. Implementation strategies: recommendations for specifying and reporting. *Implement Sci* 2013; 8: 139
[<https://doi.org/10.1186/1748-5908-8-139>][PMID: 24289295]

Appendix

Stream (Pubmed)	
A	("nursing homes"[MeSH] OR "long term care"[MeSH] OR "homes for the aged"[MeSH] OR "Skilled Nursing Facilities"[Mesh] OR nursing home*[tiab] OR long-term care[tiab] OR home for the aged[tiab] OR homes for the aged[tiab] OR nursing facilit*[tiab] OR care home*[tiab] OR residential care[tiab] OR residential aged care[tiab] OR aged care facili*[tiab] OR institutional elderly care[tiab])
B	("Implementation Science"[Mesh] OR "implementation*" [tiab] OR "initiativ*" [tiab])
C	((("Hospitalization"[Mesh] OR Hospitalization* [tiab] OR Hospitalisation* [tiab] OR "Patient Transfer"[Mesh] OR Patient Transfer* [tiab] OR "Patient Readmission"[Mesh] OR patient readmission[tiab] OR hospital admission* [tiab] OR hospital transfer* [tiab] OR hospital transition* [tiab] OR hospital transferal* [tiab] OR patient transition* [tiab] OR care transition* [tiab] OR resident transfer*[tiab]) AND (unplanned [tiab] OR avoid* [tiab] OR prevent* [tiab] OR unprevent*[tiab] OR appropriat* [tiab] OR inappropriate* [tiab] OR suitable [tiab]))
Combination	("nursing homes"[MeSH] OR "long term care"[MeSH] OR "homes for the aged"[MeSH] OR "Skilled Nursing Facilities"[Mesh] OR nursing home*[tiab] OR long-term care[tiab] OR home for the aged[tiab] OR homes for the aged[tiab] OR nursing facilit*[tiab] OR care home*[tiab] OR residential care[tiab] OR residential aged care[tiab] OR aged care facili*[tiab] OR institutional elderly care[tiab]) AND (Implementation Science[Mesh] OR "implementation*" [tiab] OR "initiativ*" [tiab]) AND ((("Hospitalization"[Mesh] OR Hospitalization* [tiab] OR Hospitalisation* [tiab] OR "Patient Transfer"[Mesh] OR Patient Transfer* [tiab] OR "Patient Readmission"[Mesh] OR patient readmission[tiab] OR hospital admission* [tiab] OR hospital transfer* [tiab] OR hospital transition* [tiab] OR hospital transferal* [tiab] OR patient transition* [tiab] OR care transition* [tiab] OR resident transfer*[tiab]) AND (unplanned [tiab] OR avoid* [tiab] OR prevent* [tiab] OR unprevent*[tiab] OR appropriat* [tiab] OR inappropriate* [tiab] OR suitable [tiab]))